

Supporting Information

Module validation

The preliminary objective of our work consists in integrating evolutionary processes, such as drift and natural selection, into a process-based model capable of simulating forest dynamics that include several coexisting species. To achieve this, we used the forest gap model ForCEEPS, as described by Morin et al. (2020). In this section, we provide a detailed explanation of our validation protocol for drift and natural selection processes.

Drift validation

Drift is the random fluctuation in allele frequencies over generations (Wright 1929). Applied to the evolution of a neutral quantitative trait, drift randomly influences the population's average trait (\bar{z}) over time and can be described as a Brownian motion. If a neutral trait evolves in several initially identical populations, drift will cause them to diverge, increasing the variance of the populations' mean phenotypes ($Var(\bar{z})$) over time. The rate at which this variance increases over time (r) is inversely proportional to the effective population size (N_e) and is proportional to the additive variance (VA) within those populations (Lande 1976). The additive variance refers to the genetic variance resulting from the additive effects of alleles (see equation (1)). In our framework, we consider only the additive effects of genes and not the dominance effect; therefore, VA is equivalent to the genetic variance.

In order to validate the drift process in our model, we compared the rate at which ($Var(\bar{z})$) increases over time across 100 replicate populations in two cases: 1) in a "large" beech population initially consisting of 750 individuals (50 ForCEEPS patches) and 2) in a "small" beech population initially consisting of 150 individuals (10 ForCEEPS patches).

Due to the characteristics of the simulated populations, which include overlapping generations and a wide variation in reproductive success that depends on age and size, accurately estimating the effective population size is challenging. Additionally, r represents the increase in $Var(\bar{z})$ per generation in populations with non-overlapping generations, not per year in populations with overlapping ones. Therefore, we assume that 1) a single constant c can convert population size (N) to effective size (N_e) for both large and small populations, and 2) a single constant t_g can convert the rate of change of $Var(\bar{z})$ per unit of time to r per generation, since large and small populations share the same generation time.

$$r = \frac{VA}{2N_e} \cdot t_g = \frac{VA}{2 \cdot N \cdot c} \cdot t_g \quad (1)$$

We therefore expect that the rate of increase of $Var(\bar{z})$ for a perfectly neutral trait will be proportional to the ratio of the larger population size to the smaller one. In our case, this ratio is 5 (see equation (2)). Under natural selection, this ratio is expected to decrease, as some genotypes are negatively selected, thereby constraining the phenotypic landscape accessible to random drift.

$$\frac{r_{neutral,small}}{r_{neutral,large}} = \frac{N_{large}}{N_{small}} \quad (2)$$

To obtain a near-neutral trait, we focused on the evolution of $DrTol$ in a context without water stress, characterized by an annual precipitation of 1496 mm, an average temperature of 7 °C, and a site bucket size of 400 mm. We also set the covariations between $DrTol$, $ShTol$, and g to zero. This ensures that even if $ShTol$ and g remain under selective pressure, the evolution of $DrTol$ cannot be indirectly affected by their evolution.

A Change in average $DrTol$ variance over time between replicates

B Change in average $DrTol$ over time between replicates

Figure S.1: A. Change in the $Var(\overline{DrTol})$ over time across the 100 replicates of large (750 individuals) and small populations (150 individuals) of beech trees. Thin lines indicate the exact $Var(\overline{DrTol})$ each year for the two population types. Thick lines show the trend in $Var(\overline{DrTol})$ for the time period. **B.** Change in pseudo-neutral \overline{DrTol} over time for the 100 replicate populations (thin line). The median trajectory is represented with a thicker line.

We observed a 4.76-fold difference in the rate of increase of $Var(\overline{DrTol})$ between the small and large populations for the pseudo-neutral trait $DrTol$, which is close to the expected ratio of 5 (Fig. S.1). In contrast, the ratios for the other two evolving traits still subject to selection pressure were lower, namely 3.17 for $ShTol$ and 3.87 for g . see Fig. S.2 for change in average $ShTol$ and g over time. These findings align with the expected behavior of genetic drift in a context where natural selection is operating.

Figure S.2: B. Changes in \overline{ShTol} (A) and \overline{g} (B) over time for 100 large (750 individuals) and small

(150 individuals) populations, represented by thin lines. The median trajectory is shown with a thicker line.

Natural selection in mixture validation

To ensure that natural selection operates as expected in a multispecific context, we focused on one of the simplest scenario under which natural selection can occur. We simulated evolutionary responses in a two-species mixed forest of beech and fir located in south-eastern France (Drôme) under three climatic conditions:

1. The historical climate for this location (1950–2000), based on ERA5 land data and repeated over 300 years (Muñoz Sabater 2019).
2. A modified historical climate with a +1.5°C temperature increase and a yearly precipitation decrease of 60 mm.
3. Another modified climate scenario with a +3°C temperature increase and a 120 mm yearly precipitation reduction.

Two evolutionary scenarios were considered:

1. Phenotypic variation ($VR = 0.3$, see methods) in traits ($DrTol$, $ShTol$, and g) but no evolution (h^2 set to 0.0001 for computational purposes, treated as $h^2 = 0$).
2. Phenotypic variation with evolution (VR and $h^2 = 0.3$).

Populations were initially composed of 720 beech and 90 fir individuals. We ran 25 replicate populations for each combination of climate and evolutionary scenarios. Negative correlations between $DrTol$ and the competitive traits $ShTol$ and g were introduced, with values of 0.36 and 0.38, respectively.

We predict population sizes to decrease in the two warming scenarios due to increased mortality. Additionally, we anticipate an evolutionary response in $DrTol$, with a stronger response in the warmest climate. If $DrTol$ evolves toward higher values, $ShTol$ and g are expected to decrease due to co-selection driven by their negative correlations with $DrTol$. We predict little to no evolutionary response when h^2 is null. Demography was assessed using the median basal area across replicates (BA), while trait evolution was captured by tracking weighted average population trait values over time. Additionally, evolutionary rates in Haldanes (H_0 , see Methods) were calculated between the start and end of the selection simulations (1900–2200).

Figure S.3: Changes in the basal area (A), \overline{DrTol} (B), and Evolutionary Rates in Haldanes (C) (H_0 see methods) between year 1900 and 2200 in beech-fir mixtures forests under three climate types: 1) historical, 2) +1.5°C/-60 mm, and 3) +3°C/-120 mm. In each case, two evolutionary scenarios were also explored: 1) $h^2 = 0.3$ and $VR = 0.3$ and 2) $h^2 = 0$, $VR = 0.3$ (no evolution).

The artificial warming impacted demography, particularly in the warmest climate (Fig. S.3.A). In response, \overline{DrTol} increased over time through natural selection in the evolutionary scenario where evolution was possible (h^2 and $VR = 0.3$), with a stronger response observed in the warmest climate (Fig. S.3 B & C). The simulated evolutionary rates were at the higher end of those observed in real plant populations responding to sudden environmental changes (Bone & Farres 2001). Unlike the drift validation simulations, the values of the two competitive traits ($ShTol$ and g) decreased as \overline{DrTol} increased. This was particularly evident in the warmest climate, indicating that trait correlations influenced evolutionary trajectories as expected (Fig. S.4 A & B). In the absence of evolution ($h^2 = 0$), an immediate increase in median \overline{DrTol} occurred, driven by differential mortality between more tolerant and less tolerant individuals, as phenotypic variability was still present ($VR = 0.3$) (Fig. S.3.B). This response resulted into low but non-zero evolutionary rates (Fig. S.3.C). It is also worth mentioning that drift has had an impact on evolutionary trajectories, as shown by the increased variance of fir trajectories compared to those of beech. (Fig. S.3 B; Fig. S.4 A & B).

Figure S.4: Average \overline{ShTol} (A), and \bar{g} (B) change over time in beech-fir mixtures forests under three climate types (no warming, +1.5°C/-60 mm, and +3°C/-120 mm) with ($h^2 = 0.3$, $VR = 0.3$) and without evolution ($h^2 = 0$, $VR = 0.3$). Thin lines represent a trajectory for one replicate population. Thick lines represent the median trajectories of all replicates. The right panels show the evolutionary rates in Haldanes (H_0 see methods) of $ShTol$ (C) and g (D).

ForCEEPS species pool trait values

Species Name	g	DrTol	ShTol
<i>Abies alba</i>	350	0.23	1
<i>Larix decidua</i>	170	0.25	9
<i>Picea abies</i>	355	0.11	5
<i>Pinus cembra</i>	115	0.3	5
<i>Pinus montana</i>	138	0.37	9
<i>Pinus sylvestris</i>	150	0.37	9
<i>Taxus baccata</i>	47	0.23	3
<i>Acer campestre</i>	156	0.33	5
<i>Acer platanoides</i>	142	0.25	4
<i>Acer pseudoplatanus</i>	125	0.25	4
<i>Alnus glutinosa</i>	250	0.08	5

Species Name	g	$DrTol$	$ShTol$
Alnus incana	266	0.08	7
Alnus viridis	531	0.16	7
Betula pendula	278	0.22	9
Carpinus betulus	300	0.25	3
Castanea sativa	142	0.33	5
Corylus avellana	95	0.33	6
Fagus sylvatica	260	0.25	1
Fraxinus excelsior	177	0.16	6
Populus nigra	285	0.08	5
Populus tremula	310	0.25	7
Quercus petraea	246	0.33	7
Quercus pubescens	146	0.33	7
Quercus robur	249	0.3	9
Salix alba	278	0.08	5
Sorbus aria	82	0.33	7
Sorbus aucuparia	167	0.33	7
Tilia cordata	114	0.33	5
Tilia platyphyllos	110	0.25	3
Ulmus glabra	153	0.25	3
Pinus pinaster	350	0.4	7
Pinus nigra	175	0.23	7
Pinus halepensis	162	0.48	7
Pseudotsuga menziesii	492	0.15	3
Quercus ilex	79	0.45	5

Table S.1: Values of the parameters g , $DrTol$, and $ShTol$ for all species calibrated for ForCEEPS.

These values were used to calculate the interspecific standard deviation of traits ($\overrightarrow{sd_{inter}}$), which are 111, 0.099, and 2.16 respectively for g , $DrTol$, and $ShTol$.

Site description

Site	Bucket Size (cm)	Nitrogen Content	Latitude	Longitude	KEstNr	Max Evap° Rate (%)	Fraction Intercepted rain
Drôme (26)	10	100	44°55'01.2"N	5°17'27.6"E	0.006	12	0.3
Montagne Noire (81)	10	100	43°27'55.4"N	2°16'43.2"E	0.006	12	0.3

Table S.2 : Site specific parameters. KEstNr is the maximum seedling establishment rate (unitless).

Site	Yearly precipitations (mm)	Mean temperatures (°C)	Average tree number	Average basal area (m ² /ha)
Drôme (26)	1146	5.9	720 beech ; 90 fir	11.6 beech ; 1.91 fir
Montagne Noire (81)	983	9.3	110 beech ; 119 fir	0.21 beech ; 0.87 fir

Table S.3: Descriptive climate data and baseline simulations of the two study sites under their respective climates. Mean annual precipitation sums and mean temperatures at the coordinates of the two sites in ERA5 land data from 1969 to 2011 are provided. Under these conditions, the ForCEEPS model without an evolutionary module produces inventories with the the given average number of trees and basal area. The very low tree densities at the Montagne Noire site suggest that the initial parameters for beech and fir do not match this environment.

Assisted gene flow trait values

<i>Fagus sylvatica</i>					<i>Abies alba</i>				
<i>g</i>	VR = 0.1	VR = 0.2	VR = 0.3	VR = 0.4	<i>g</i>	VR = 0.1	VR = 0.2	VR = 0.3	VR = 0.4
<i>h</i> ² = 0.1	258.25	256.94	254.85	255.52	<i>h</i> ² = 0.1	347.96	343.31	340.29	339.27
<i>h</i> ² = 0.2	257.89	252.19	247.21	249.5	<i>h</i> ² = 0.2	345.87	340.08	335.76	339.8

<i>Fagus sylvatica</i>					<i>Abies alba</i>				
$h^2 = 0.3$	258.07	245.43	249.42	243.79	$h^2 = 0.3$	344.40	338.07	335.47	339.23
$h^2 = 0.4$	253.73	247.11	246.26	254.43	$h^2 = 0.4$	342.27	336.65	341.31	346.26
<i>DrTol</i>	<i>VR = 0.1</i>	<i>VR = 0.2</i>	<i>VR = 0.3</i>	<i>VR = 0.4</i>	<i>DrTol</i>	<i>VR = 0.1</i>	<i>VR = 0.2</i>	<i>VR = 0.3</i>	<i>VR = 0.4</i>
$h^2 = 0.1$	1.09	1.21	0.38	1.49	$h^2 = 0.1$	1.09	1.21	1.33	1.46
$h^2 = 0.2$	1.13	1.32	1.47	1.61	$h^2 = 0.2$	1.12	1.27	1.42	1.57
$h^2 = 0.3$	1.15	1.36	1.53	1.66	$h^2 = 0.3$	1.16	1.35	1.47	1.56
$h^2 = 0.4$	1.18	1.51	1.72	1.8	$h^2 = 0.4$	1.22	1.39	1.54	1.59
<i>ShTol</i>	<i>VR = 0.1</i>	<i>VR = 0.2</i>	<i>VR = 0.3</i>	<i>VR = 0.4</i>	<i>ShTol</i>	<i>VR = 0.1</i>	<i>VR = 0.2</i>	<i>VR = 0.3</i>	<i>VR = 0.4</i>
$h^2 = 0.1$	0.26	0.27	0.28	0.29	$h^2 = 0.1$	0.23	0.25	0.26	0.27
$h^2 = 0.2$	0.26	0.28	0.30	0.32	$h^2 = 0.2$	0.24	0.26	0.27	0.28
$h^2 = 0.3$	0.27	0.29	0.31	0.33	$h^2 = 0.3$	0.25	0.27	0.28	0.29
$h^2 = 0.4$	0.27	0.31	0.33	0.34	$h^2 = 0.4$	0.25	0.27	0.29	0.30

Table S.4: Average trait values of migrant individuals added to the simulations during the warming period in the assisted gene flow treatment for each of the 16 evolutionary scenarios for question 2. These values were obtained from a thousand years of simulations under the historical climate conditions of the Montagne Noire site.

Trait correlations

Trait correlation values are based on interspecific trait correlations found in the literature and databases. To maximize the species pool used to compute these correlations, we focused on correlations between proxies for our three evolving parameters: *DrTol*, *ShTol*, and *g*. We used drought tolerance (*NiiDrTol*) and shade tolerance (*NiiShTol*) rankings from Niinemets and Valladares (2006) as proxies for *DrTol* and *ShTol*, respectively. For *g*, we used relative growth

rates (RGR) from the TRY database (Kattge *et al.* 2020) as a proxy. The RGR data were filtered to include only observations under the least restrictive growth conditions (full light exposure, nutrient-enriched substrate and maximal watering) from available sources. RGR values were averaged per species and data source and then averaged across all data sources for each species, giving equal weighting to each source. The species included in this analysis were those considered native in the meta-analysis by Niinemets and Valladares (2006), for which RGR data were available in the TRY database (Fig. S.5).

Figure S.5: Correlations between three proxies of ForCEEPS g, ShTol and DrTol, respectively: Relative Growth Rate (*RGR*) (g/g/day) from a compilation in the TRY database (Kattge *et al.*, 2020), *NiiShTol* and *NiiDrTol* (shade and drought tolerance rankings) (Niinemets & Valladares, 2006). The diagonal part of the plot matrix shows the density distribution of the three variables, the lower part of the figure displays the scatter plot of each variable in relation to the others, and the upper part shows the corresponding Pearson correlation coefficients.

Simulation plan

Figure S.6: Simulation plan for addressing the three main objectives of the article (see introduction).

Figure S.7: **A.** Time series of the median across replicates of basal area and tree number in beech populations for an evolutionary scenario of type h^2 and $VR = 0.3$. The two vertical segments indicate the basal area and the year corresponding to the pre-warming date and the minimum basal area of the simulation. **B.** Distribution of the median number of trees across replicates by height class in 1-meter segments. A dotted horizontal line shows the median maximum number of trees among fir height classes, providing an order-of-magnitude comparison with beech population sizes. The sum of the heights of all the red bars gives the minimum median number of trees in the treatment, i.e., 26 for fir and 316.5 for beech.

Median minimal relative basal area with population size (RBA) (%)

Figure S.8: Median minimal relative forest basal area in a forest of Drôme site for the various scenarios of heritability (h^2) and intra- to interspecific trait standard deviation ratio (VR) (as in Fig. 2). The numbers of replicates are indicated under the treatment type. In contrast to Fig. 2, numerical values in white show the median across replicates of the population size (instead of basal area) in the year when the basal area of the simulation is the smallest. As a reminder, the mixture, assisted gene flow and assisted migration treatments were carried out on 5-hectare forests, while the fir and beech monospecific simulations were carried out on forests of 1.1 ha and 4.2 ha respectively, to keep species population sizes within the same order of magnitude, as shown in the figure.

Light availability

Figure S.9: Median across replicates ($n = 50$ for monospecific and beech-fir mixtures; $n = 25$ for assisted gene flow and assisted migration treatments) of individual light availability (%) (i.e. averaged across all individuals per species) over time for beech and fir populations under all evolutionary scenarios. The line stops when every population goes extinct in a given evolutionary scenario.

Short term evolutionary rates

Figure S.10: Evolutionary rates in Haldanes (H_0) for fir and beech from 2000 to 2100 (warming period) across the four h^2 evolutionary scenarios with $VR = 0.3$, shown for the three traits: *DrTol* (A), *ShTol* (B), and *g* (C). Other VR scenarios are not included because Haldane's rates are standardized by trait variation. Thus, by definition, VR cannot alter the evolutionary rates.

Long term evolutionary changes

To assess long-term evolutionary trajectories, the the weighted average trait \bar{z} differences for each species (s) between the reference period and the final year (year 3000) of the simulation were calculated. The weights correspond to the relative BA of each individual as a proportion of the total BA of its species. For details, see equation (3).

$$\Delta z_s = \overline{z_{3000,s}} - \frac{1}{500} \sum_{y=1500}^{2000} \overline{z_{y,s}} \quad \text{with} \quad \overline{z_{y,s}} = \sum_{i=1}^N z_{i,y,s} \cdot \text{weight}_{i,y,s} \quad (3)$$

Figure S.11: Average weighted $DrTol$ difference (Δ_{DrTol}) for beech and fir between the reference period (1500-2000) and the final year of the simulation (3000). A box plot is displayed when more than 10 replicates experienced evolutionary rescue.

Figure S.12: Average weighted $ShTol$ difference (Δ_{ShTol}) for beech and fir between the reference period (1500-2000) and the final year of the simulation (3000).

Figure S.13: Average weighted g difference (Δ_g) for beech and fir between the reference period (1500-2000) and the final year of the simulation (3000).

Species traits evolutionary trajectories

$h^2 = 0.3$ & $VR = 0.3$

Fir

Beech

Species

Figure S.14: Details of weighted average trait values in two dimensions over time for each replicate (thin lines). Line transparency reflects the passage of time, with greater transparency in year 1000 and no transparency in year 3000. The general direction of time is from the bottom right to the top left. Dots indicate the final trait values of a population (year 3000), while crosses mark the trait values at the year of population extinction. Horizontal and vertical lines represent the median final trait values across replicates for a given treatment.

References

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